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Development and application of a new Resilient, Sustainable, Safe and Inclusive Community Rating System (RESSICOM)

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Abstract The rising concern about sustainable development led most states worldwide to adopt the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development to achieve 17 new goals before the end of 2030. Due to the prominent role of urbanization, the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) #11 was introduced to make cities and human settlements more resilient, sustainable, safe and inclusive. The frameworks built so far to assess sustainable urban development primarily focus on sustainability, disregarding inclusiveness, safety and resilience. Under the joint consideration of these four facets, this research devised a new tool to evaluate communities and cities by selecting 61 indicators from an extensive literature review, which were weighted subsequently to ensure the balance among the four sustainability dimensions, namely society, economy, environment and governance. Data extracted from international organizations and the targets of the SDGs were used to score the indicators of the system. Mexico City, as one of the most overcrowded cities in the planet, was selected as a case study to apply the proposed tool. The research determined that the minimum thresholds set for the safety, sustainability and inclusiveness domains were not reached. In contrast, the city performed over the resilience limit. Consequently, RESSICOM was revealed as a helpful framework to identify shortcomings in cities related to the achievement of SDG #11.

Keywords Inclusiveness; Resilience; Safety; Sustainable Development; Sustainable Development Goals; Urbanization.

1. Introduction

The Habitat I Conference held in Vancouver in 1976 recognized urbanization as a global issue derived from the rapid concentration of population in urban settlements (UN, 1976). Since then, urban dwellers have increased from 1.56 to 4.2 billion in 2018, being expected to rise 2.5 billion more by 2050 (UN, 2018). Despite 70% of world Gross Domestic Product is generated in urban areas, more than 1 billion slum dwellers live in cities lacking basic services (UN-Habitat, 2016), whilst one third of urban residents are poor (Ravallion et al., 2007), revealing the close connection between urban poverty and the population shift to cities (Tannerfeldt and Ljung, 2012).

42 The Brundtland Commission coined the term Sustainable Development in 1987 as
43 the flagship to preserve the capacity of future generations to meet their own needs as
44 long as the present necessities are covered (WCED, 1987). In 1992, the Agenda 21 was
45 adopted in the Earth Summit held in Rio, emphasizing the role of the environmental,
46 social and economic dimensions in the construction of a better world (UN, 1992). Simi-
47 larly, urban sustainability can be defined as the ability of meeting essential needs of
48 inhabitants without exceeding environmental constraints and balancing economic, social
49 and environmental goals across an inclusive and participatory governance
50 (Satterthwaite, 1997). The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2015) seeks
51 to fulfil 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through a global commitment in-
52 volving all relevant stakeholders coordinated at different scale levels of governance
53 (Cohen, 2006). SDG #11 (“Sustainable Cities and Communities”) focuses on major
54 urban concerns to enhance the sustainability, resilience, safety and inclusiveness of cit-
55 ies. The New Urban Agenda adopted by the international community in October 2016
56 (Habitat III, 2016) is also aligned with the achievement of SDG #11.

57 If the role of urbanization in sustainability is prominent, its linkage with resilience is
58 no less powerful (Meerow et al., 2016). Past natural disasters in urban areas highlighted
59 the need to develop response systems to extreme events (Cutter et al., 2013) and persis-
60 tent stress (Folke and Gunderson, 2010). Although resilience covers a wide range of
61 definitions, the National Academy of Sciences emphasized its ability to plan for, absorb,
62 recover from and adapt to hazards (NAS, 2012), whilst the Intergovernmental Panel on
63 Climate Change also incorporated the preservation, restoration or enhancement of criti-
64 cal systems and functions (IPCC, 2012). Sustainability and resilience show many com-
65 monalities, but also some differences in terms of space and time. Whilst the former is
66 associated with greater spaces and prolonged time periods, the latter affects smaller are-
67 as more quickly (Marchese et al., 2018). However, both concepts are proportional: the
68 more resilient a system, the greater its sustainability (Ahern, 2013).

69 The participation of citizens in decision-making processes (Pouw and Gupta, 2017),
70 the respect of human rights (Arts, 2017) or the defense of marginalized and indigenous
71 communities (Ballard, 2005) underlie the concept of inclusiveness, mostly focused on
72 the social dimension of sustainability. Disadvantaged groups are especially vulnerable
73 to hazards from climate change and income inequalities, unemployment, lack of basic
74 services or access to health and education (Fritz and Koch, 2014).

75 Safety awareness concern related to livability and quality of life in cities (Finka and
76 Kluvánková, 2015) is accentuated by the effects of growing urbanization (Li et al.,
77 2012) in terms of population density and city size (Zhang and Li, 2018). Core urban
78 safety problems to be deemed are, inter alia, hazards, crime and traffic safety (Vieira
79 Gomes et al., 2012).

80 Several systems were created to assess sustainable development and resilience. The
81 US Green Building Council built the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design

82 Neighborhood Development (LEED ND) framework (USGBC, 2018), oriented to as-
83 sess developments with at least two habitable buildings and no larger than 1,500 acres,
84 and the LEED Cities and Communities Pilot, focused on cities (USGBC, 2018). Fur-
85 thermore, the Building Research Establishment Assessment Method Communities
86 (BREEAM Communities) (BREEAM, 2018) was presented in the United Kingdom to
87 appraise the social, economic and environmental impacts at neighborhood or larger
88 scales. Later, American experts produced the Sustainability Tool for Assessing and Rat-
89 ing (STAR) Communities to enhance the sustainability of cities in the United States
90 (STAR Communities, 2018). The Japanese Institute for Building Environment and En-
91 ergy Conservation developed CASBEE for Cities (CASBEE, 2018) to implement indi-
92 cators comprised in the SDGs and the ISO 37120 standard (ISO, 2018a) for all world-
93 wide countries. Aiming at integrating sustainable actions and stakeholder participation
94 in communities, the Green Building Council of Australia designed the Green Star
95 Communities framework (GBCA, 2018). With regard to resilience, the City Resilience
96 Index (ARUP, 2015) and the City Resilience Profiling Tool (UN-Habitat, 2012) were
97 developed to be applied worldwide. The former was created by the Rockefeller Founda-
98 tion and Arup to assess diverse factors affecting urban resilience, whilst the latter was
99 powered by UN-Habitat to appraise resilience to multi-hazard disasters. Additionally,
100 specific actions were led by the US National Institute of Standards and Technology
101 through diverse tools and methods. The Geospatial Risk and Resilience Assessment
102 Platform created in 2016, as well as the Communities Advancing Resilience Toolkit
103 (Pfefferbaum et al., 2013) and the Baseline Resilience Indicators for Communities
104 (Cutter et al., 2010) are other frameworks focused on the assessment of resilience.

105 As revealed by the literature review, existing tools were not conceived to appraise
106 urban settlements under the joint vision of resilience, sustainability, inclusiveness and
107 safety. Thus, this research aimed at bridging this gap by developing a new urban tool
108 contemplating these four facets and equally pondering the four sustainability dimen-
109 sions. The methodology followed to build the new rating system was applied to Mexico
110 City as a representative case study, due to its high population and historic exposure to
111 disasters.

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113 **2. Methodology**

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115 The tiered approach of the proposed methodology is shown in Figure 1. After undertak-
116 ing a deep literature review to gather information on metrics, frameworks and global
117 statistical databases related to urban sustainability, resilience, inclusiveness and safety, a
118 set of indicators was selected covering the four major aims contemplated by the SDG
119 #11 and substantiated by the New Urban Agenda. In line with worldwide statistics at
120 different level scale governments and SDGs, minimum and maximum scores were es-

121 established for each indicator. The weights of the indicators were determined by equally
 122 balancing the four dimensions of sustainable development.

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Figure 1. Tiered approach for the design of RESSICOM

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128 **2.1. Selection of indicators**

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130 Different criteria were applied to identify the set of indicators to cover the four domains
 131 on which the new Resilient, Sustainable, Safe and Inclusive Community Rating System
 132 (RESSICOM) is based. Firstly, a deep analysis of provisions concerning major present
 133 global initiatives was performed, such as the 2030 Agenda, the New Urban Agenda and
 134 the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (UNISDR, 2015).

135 Excluding SDG #15 (“Life below water”), all SDGs were taken into account to
 136 avoid any bias towards coastal cities. Although SDG #11 was explicitly conceived to
 137 address urban issues, the wide scope of sustainable development required incorporating
 138 targets of the remaining SDGs, such that RESSICOM could consider the 3 P’s of sus-
 139 tainability: planet, people and prosperity (Hammond, 2006). The New Urban Agenda
 140 also reaffirmed the commitment of worldwide countries to meet the SDGs, especially
 141 SDG #11. Regarding the Sendai Framework, RESSICOM compiles some of its targets
 142 associated with the disruption of basic services and the availability of hazard early
 143 warning systems.

144 The main features of resilience, namely absorption, adaptation and recovery suggest
 145 that cities should be inclusive (Ding et al., 2015), integrated (Redman, 2014), robust
 146 (Wamsler et al., 2013), resourceful (Ernst et al., 2016), reflective (Woolf et al., 2016)
 147 and redundant (Pandit et al., 2017).

148 The massive arrival of migrants to cities creates marginalised groups lacking access
 149 to, inter alia, job opportunities, basic services, health and education. Some indicators are
 150 thus needed to assess the capability of cities to promote inclusiveness among new resi-
 151 dents. Furthermore, the provision of critical services is essential to urban dwellers in
 152 terms of adequacy (resources), operation in case of disruptions (robustness) and redun-
 153 dancy to ensure service performance. Since urban settlements are the compilation of
 154 different interconnected systems to create a functioning whole (Allan and Bryant,
 155 2011), this integration must be monitored through the evaluation of local government
 156 instruments, enabling the revision and update of policies and plans based on past expe-
 157 riences. The identification of core points to be tracked by new indicators was undertak-
 158 en after an extensive literature review.

159 As listed in Table 1, the resilience category contemplates 8 indicators. RES.1 moni-
 160 tors electric power supply through the System Average Interruption Duration In-
 161 dex (SAIDI), which is calculated as the ratio of the sum of all customer interruption
 162 durations to the total number of customers served (NEXT, 2018). RES.2 quantifies the
 163 total annual hours of cuts in water supply affecting at least 10% of population according
 164 to ISO TC-224 (ISO, 2018b). The existence of an open-source map including exposure
 165 and vulnerability to main urban hazards is scored by RES.3. RES.4 assesses regularly
 166 redundancy of critical urban services: water, power, education and health. The imple-
 167 mentation, update and conduct of regular simulations involving early warning systems
 168 and emergency plans are evaluated by RES.5 and RES.6, respectively. The performance
 169 of educational and health services is crucial to ensure a normal urban life, whereby at
 170 least 80% of both services is required. Disruptions suffered by learning and health facil-
 171 ities are rated by RES.7 and RES.8.

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Table 1. List of indicators to assess urban resilience

RES.#	Concept	Units
RES.1	Power Disruptions	minutes
RES.2	Water Disruptions	hours
RES.3	Risk Map	yes/no
RES.4	Redundancy Critical Services	yes/no
RES.5	Early Warning Systems	yes/no
RES.6	Emergency Plan & Drills	yes/no
RES.7	Health Services Disruptions	days
RES.8	Educational Services Disruptions	days

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175 Regarding the sustainability indicators shown in Table 2, SUS.1 evaluates the pro-
 176 portion of family income spent on housing, including power and water. The rate of re-
 177 duction on power and water consumption is granted by SUS.2 and SUS.4. Whilst the
 178 use of renewable sources is marked by SUS.3, SUS.5 appraises losses of drinkable wa-
 179 ter from urban network leakages. Public and updated information covering organization
 180 and responsibilities of all municipal bodies is the aim of SUS.6. SUS.7 covers the pro-

181 portion of adult population (aged 15 and over) showing a Body Mass Index above 25%.
 182 The population who commutes to work by walking or bicycling is rated by SUS.8. An-
 183 nual fares per capita on public transport are contemplated in SUS.9, whilst the hours
 184 spent on traffic jams during yearly working days is measured by SUS.10. The surface of
 185 urban public green areas and land consumption per inhabitant are appraised by SUS.11
 186 and SUS.12. SUS.13, SUS.14, SUS.15 and SUS.16 were set to grade air emissions per
 187 capita of major pollutants impacting human health and the environment, such as PM_{2.5},
 188 NO₂, SO₂ and carbon. The ratio of city budget externally funded is monitored by
 189 SUS.17, whilst SUS.19 assesses the percentage of population employed in the manufac-
 190 turing sector. Satisfaction of citizens with judicial, educational and health services is
 191 reflected by SUS.20, whilst the proportion of solid waste recycled is covered by
 192 SUS.21.

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Table 2. List of indicators to assess urban sustainability

SUS.#	Concept	Units
SUS.1	Household Spending on Housing	%
SUS.2	Reduction on Energy Use	%
SUS.3	Renewable Energy	%
SUS.4	Reduction on Water Consumption	%
SUS.5	Losses from Urban Water Network	%
SUS.6	Municipal Liabilities Description	yes/no
SUS.7	Overweight Adults	%
SUS.8	Walking/Bicycling Work Commute	%
SUS.9	Use of Public Transport	trips/year
SUS.10	Traffic Congestion	hours
SUS.11	Public Open Green Areas	m ² per capita
SUS.12	Land Consumption	m ² per capita
SUS.13	PM _{2.5} Concentration	μg/m ³
SUS.14	NO ₂ Concentration	μg/m ³
SUS.15	SO ₂ Concentration	μg/m ³
SUS.16	Carbon Emissions per Capita	ton/year
SUS.17	Municipal Debt	%
SUS.18	Local Expenditure in Essential Services	%
SUS.19	Manufacturing Employment	%
SUS.20	Effectiveness of Public Services	%
SUS.21	Solid Waste Recycling	%

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Table 3 gathers the indicators selected to appraise the safety domain. People living under the current international limit of poverty (USD 1.90 a day) is scored by SAF.1, whereas SAF.2 grades the ratio of children under five suffering from malnutrition. Regular access to power, drinkable water and sanitation facilities are measured by SAF.3, SAF.4 and SAF.5. The total unemployment ratio encompassing both genders is represented by SAF.6. Corruption scourge is rated through the implementation of transparent

202 systems (SAF.7) and the proportion of urban dwellers forced to pay bribes to access to
 203 public services during the last year (SAF.8). Robberies and homicides per 100,000 in-
 204 habitants are the targets of SAF.9 and SAF.10. The proportion of people who feel safe
 205 in cities is covered by SAF.11. Three major health issues are addressed by SAF.12,
 206 SAF.13 and SAF.14. The first one quantifies the minutes taken from the initial emer-
 207 gency call to the arrival of the first responders, whilst the second and third metrics focus
 208 on the coverage of public health insurance systems and the amount of public hospital
 209 beds per 1,000 inhabitants, respectively. Lastly, the recipients of regular solid waste
 210 collection in cities are reflected by SAF.15.

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Table 3. List of indicators to assess urban safety

SAF.#	Concept	Units
SAF.1	People Living in Poverty	%
SAF.2	Child Malnutrition	%
SAF.3	Power Supply	%
SAF.4	Drinkable Water Supply	%
SAF.5	Sanitation Facilities	%
SAF.6	Total Unemployment Rate	%
SAF.7	Fight Against Corruption	yes/no
SAF.8	Corruption in Public Sector	%
SAF.9	Robberies Rate	robberies per 100,000 inhabitants
SAF.10	Homicide Rate	homicides per 100,000 inhabitants
SAF.11	Personal Security	%
SAF.12	Time for Emergency Response	minutes
SAF.13	Basic Public Health Insurance Coverage	%
SAF.14	Public Hospital In-patient Beds	%
SAF.15	Solid Waste Collection	%

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As part of urban inclusiveness (Table 4), INC.1 and INC.2 represent the proportion of slum dwellers and homeless population in cities. INC.3 scores the existence of an updated map indicating all stakeholders concerned with resilience and sustainability matters. The implementation of binding public consultations to promote the involvement of population in local government and the rate of eligible voters who participated in the last municipal election are the aims of INC.4 and INC.5. INC.6 and INC.7 appraise proportion of young people (from 15 to 24 years) working and informal employment, respectively. The salary gap between genders and the endorsement of labour policies addressed to promote employment among low-income and minority groups are covered by INC.8 and INC.9. INC.10 represents the GINI coefficient, a global indicator measuring inequality (StatsDirect, 2018). The proportion of youth people (both sexes) and females enrolled in the first year of secondary school from primary education are tracked by INC.11 and INC.12. The average time spent on commuting to or from work is scored by INC.13. The rate of population with internet connection (broadband or mobile) is assessed by INC.14. INC.15, INC.16 and INC.17 evaluate the implementation of

229 effective policies to promote migrants inclusion, the proportion of migrants in urban
230 areas and the existence of census addressed to indigenous individuals, respectively.
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Table 4. List of indicators to assess urban inclusiveness

INC.#	Concept	Units
INC.1	Slum Dwellers	%
INC.2	Homeless	%
INC.3	Sustainability & Resilience Stakeholders Mapping	yes/no
INC.4	Social Involvement	yes/no
INC.5	Voter Turnout in Last Local Election	%
INC.6	Youth Unemployment Rate	%
INC.7	Informal Employment	%
INC.8	Gender Wage Gap	%
INC.9	Labour Inclusiveness	yes/no
INC.10	GINI Coefficient	GINI coef.
INC.11	Secondary Education Enrolment	%
INC.12	Female Rate in Secondary School	%
INC.13	Commuting Time	minutes
INC.14	Internet Connections	%
INC.15	Implementation of Migration Policies	yes/no
INC.16	Migration Population Rate	%
INC.17	Indigenous Population Registration	yes/no

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After a wide literature review and the analysis of the 2030 Agenda, the New Urban Agenda and the Sendai Framework, RESSICOM was organized as a set of 61 indicators grouped into four categories involving 8, 21, 15 and 17 metrics related to resilience, sustainability, safety and inclusiveness, respectively.

2.2. Determination of scores for the indicators

The thresholds used to assign the highest grades to RESSICOM metrics were based on SDGs' targets expiring at the end of 2030. Since 2030 corresponds to a long term view, some intermediate scores were provided for earlier dates. However, other indicators not directly connected with the SDGs were linked with data extracted from international organizations. The upper (U) and lower (L) scores and the thresholds for each RESSICOM indicator are reflected in Table 5. All lower boundaries were deemed as mandatory.

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Table 5. Upper (U) and lower (L) scores and thresholds (T) of RESSICOM indicators

RES.#	U _{RES} /T _{RES}	L _{RES} /T _{RES}	SUS.#	U _{SUS} /T _{SUS}	L _{SUS} /T _{SUS}	SAF.#	U _{SAF} /T _{SAF}	L _{SAF} /T _{SAF}	INC.#	U _{INC} /T _{INC}	L _{INC} /T _{INC}
RES.1	3/<30	1/90-120	SUS.1	2/<15	1/15-30	SAF.1	2/0	1/0-10	INC.1	2/<5	1/5-15
RES.2	3/<8	2/8-16	SUS.2	3/>80	1/40-60	SAF.2	2/<2.5	1/2.5-5	INC.2	2/<1	1/1-5
RES.3	2/yes	2/yes	SUS.3	2/>20	1/18-20	SAF.3	2/100	1/90-100	INC.3	1/yes	1/yes
RES.4	2/yes	2/yes	SUS.4	3/>40	1/20-30	SAF.4	2/100	2/100	INC.4	1/yes	1/yes
RES.5	2/yes	1/no	SUS.5	3/<5	2/5-15	SAF.5	2/100	2/100	INC.5	3/>70	1/50-60
RES.6	2/yes	1/no	SUS.6	1/yes	1/yes	SAF.6	3/<10	2/10-15	INC.6	3/<10	2/10-15
RES.7	2/<3	1/3-6	SUS.7	2/<10	1/10-20	SAF.7	2/yes	2/yes	INC.7	2/<10	1/10-20
RES.8	2/<6	1/6-12	SUS.8	3/>25	1/5-15	SAF.8	2/<5	1/5-15	INC.8	2/<5	1/5-10
			SUS.9	3/>900	2/600-900	SAF.9	3/<50	1/100-150	INC.9	1/yes	1/yes
			SUS.10	2/<20	1/20-40	SAF.10	2/<5	1/5-15	INC.10	1/0	0.6/0.4
			SUS.11	2/>9	1/5-9	SAF.11	3/>90	2/75-90	INC.11	3/100	2/80-100
			SUS.12	3/>250	1/50-150	SAF.12	2/<4	1/4-8	INC.12	2/>92	1/84-92
			SUS.13	3/<5	2/5-15	SAF.13	3/100	2/80-100	INC.13	3/<30	1/60-90
			SUS.14	3/<10	2/10-25	SAF.14	3/>7	1/2-4.5	INC.14	3/>90	1/50-75
			SUS.15	3/<25	2/25-75	SAF.15	1/100	1/100	INC.15	2/yes	1/no
			SUS.16	3/<5	2/5-15				INC.16	2/>25	0/<15
			SUS.17	1/<10	0/>=10				INC.17	2/yes	1/no
			SUS.18	3/>20	1/10-15						
			SUS.19	2/>20	1/10-20						
			SUS.20	3/>90	1/64-77						
			SUS.21	3/>75	1/25-50						
Resilience	18	11	Sustainability	53	26	Safety	34	21	Inclusiveness	35	17.60

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The thresholds for RES.1 were established after considering SAIDI data from European regulators (CEER, 2017), such that the minimum grade corresponds to a value between 90 and 120 minutes. The EU Water Framework Directive (European Commission, 2000) determines the score of RES.2, whereby 2 points are demanded to represent a yearly disruption length between 8 and 16 hours affecting more than 90% of citizens. RES.3 and RES.4 required the regular update of risk maps and redundancy reports to earn 2 points, whilst RES.5 and RES.6 were awarded with 1 point due to the existence of early warning systems and emergency plans. RES.7 and RES.8 were obtained from the knowledge platform for disaster risk reduction of United Nations (UNISDR, 2018). 1 mark is requested to ensure an interruption between 3 to 6 days and 6 to 12 days for health facilities and learning centres, respectively.

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SUS.1, SUS.2, SUS.3 and SUS.4 were graded according to the SDGs. 1 compulsory mark is demanded to each of them, in order to spend between 15 and 30% of family income on housing, reduce energy use between 40 and 60%, use from 18 to 20% energy from renewable sources and decrease domestic water use between 20 and 30%. The evaluation of SUS.5 is based on the European water directive. Permissible leakages range from 5 to 15% lead to gain 2 points. 1 point was allocated to SUS.6 when holding a public description of the responsibilities assigned to all municipal departments. The proportion of overweight population aged over 15 years should be between 10 and 20% to reach 1 point in SUS.7 (ENSANUT, 2016).

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The OECD database (OECD, 2018) was used to score SUS.8, SUS.11, SUS.12, SUS.17, SUS.18, SUS.19 and SUS.21. Having between 5 and 15% of the population walking or bicycling to work is required to get 1 point in SUS.8. Whilst a ratio per capita of 5 to 9 m² of public green areas was set to reach the needed point in SUS.11, land consumption per person should be between 50 to 150 m² to reach the minimum threshold in SUS.12. No mark is requested for SUS.17, because some councils can be heavily indebted due to the lack of economic transfers from central governments. However, the proportion of municipal budget spent on judicial, health and education services (SUS.18) should be between 10 to 15% to earn 1 mark. From 10 to 20% of the working population should be employed in manufacturing (SUS.19) to receive the mandatory point. The recycling of solid waste collected in cities (SUS.21) requests a proportion between 25 and 50% to be rewarded with the required mark.

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SUS.9 rates annual fares per inhabitant. According to the International Association for Public Transport statistics (UITP, 2017), from 600 to 900 urban trips per year is the value requested to gain 2 points. The INRIX Global Traffic Scorecard (INRIX, 2018) provides information to grade SUS.10, which should reach at least 1 mark by amounting from 20 to 40 annual hours spent in congestions. The European Air Quality standards (European Commission, 2008) were deemed to score SUS.13, SUS.14, SUS.15 and SUS.16. In all cases, two points are compulsory to ensure concentration values from 5

292 to 15, 10 to 25 and 25 to 50 for the first three metrics, respectively, and from 5 to 15
293 tons of CO₂ equivalent for the yearly emissions of carbon. Finally, the satisfaction of
294 urban residents with educational, health and judicial services (SUS.20) was graded us-
295 ing OECD statistics (OECD, 2017).

296 World Bank data determined the ratings of SAF.1, SAF.3, SAF.4, SAF.5 and SAF.6
297 (World Bank, 2018). From 0 to 10% of urban population living with USD 1.90 a day
298 (SAF.1) is scored with one mandatory mark. RESSICOM demands that 90 to 100% of
299 dwellers can regularly access to basic services. Whilst power supply access (SAF.3) is
300 rewarded with 1 mandatory point, drinkable water (SAF.4) and sanitation (SAF.5) facil-
301 ities are graded with 2 marks each. SAF.6 requires a minimum score of 2 points for an
302 unemployment ratio between 10 and 15%. Another point is associated with values be-
303 tween 2.5 and 5% of children under 5 years suffering from malnutrition (SAF.2) (WHO,
304 2017). SAF.7 receives 2 mandatory points by implementing transparent systems to pre-
305 vent corruption and allowing public access to periodic reports. Results from a global
306 survey tracking corruption practices (Transparency International, 2013) were deemed to
307 grade SAF.8, which received 1 point when 5 to 15% of the population bribed in the last
308 12 months.

309 Statistics of crime in connection with SAF.9 and SAF.10 were extracted from World
310 Bank data (World Bank, 2018). In both cases, one point is required to achieve a rate of
311 incidents per 100,000 inhabitants between 100 and 150 for robberies and from 5 to 15%
312 for homicides. The Safe Cities Index (The Economist, 2015) was used to rate SAF.11.
313 Between 75 and 90% of urban population must feel safe to reward this indicator with 2
314 marks. National Fire Protection Association standards were used to score SAF.12. A
315 range of 4 to 8 minutes is demanded to achieve 1 mandatory point (NFPA, 2016).
316 Whilst two marks are granted when 80 to 100% of population is covered by public
317 health services (SAF.13), only one point was awarded for rates between 2 and 4.5 pub-
318 lic hospital beds per 1,000 inhabitants (SAF.14) (WHO, 2017). In case solid waste col-
319 lection covers the whole urban population, SAF.15 is scored with 1 point.

320 The ratings of INC.1, INC.2, INC.6, INC.7, INC.10, INC.14 and INC.16 stem from
321 World Bank information (World Bank, 2018). 1 point is scored if the slum dwellers
322 ratio ranges from 5 to 15% (INC.1) and the homeless proportion is between 1 and 5%
323 (INC.2). A youth unemployment ratio (INC.6) between 10 and 15% is granted with 2
324 points, whilst INC.7 receives 1 point for informal employment rates between 10 and
325 20%. Inequality is globally assessed by the GINI coefficient (StatsDirect, 2018), such
326 that INC.10 is required to earn 0.6 points to reach the average value worldwide (0.4).
327 Total population with internet connection must be between 50 and 75% to achieve the
328 mandatory mark of INC.14. No minimum score is requested to migration population
329 rate (INC.16), because the reasons why migrants move to urban areas are often not di-
330 rectly attributable to cities, but rather to national or global conditions.

331 The implementation of diverse practices and policies was set to earn the mandatory
332 marks of INC.3, INC.9, INC.15 and INC.17, including publicly accessible description
333 of local government stakeholders involved in sustainability and resilience matters, labor
334 policies to foster the integration of low-income and minority groups, policies to facili-
335 tate inclusiveness of migrants and a census to register indigenous people, respectively.
336 Furthermore, INC.4 requires at least one binding consultation related to urban develop-
337 ment actions to receive its mandatory point.

338 INC.5 grades 1 compulsory point when the participation rate in the last municipal
339 poll was between 50 and 60%, whilst the proportion of salary gap between males and
340 females (INC.8) must be in the range from 5 to 10% to receive the requested mark
341 (OECD, 2017). INC.11 and INC.12 were graded according to the SDGs targets. To gain
342 the 2 requested marks, between 80 and 100% of youth people from both genders should
343 be enrolled in secondary school (INC.11). Moreover, from 84 to 92% of females finish-
344 ing primary studies should begin secondary education to earn 1 mark (INC.12). Lastly,
345 INC.13 score was scored according to the UITP. Between 60 and 90 minutes as average
346 time to commute to work are necessary to receive the mandatory point (UITP, 2017).

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348 **2.3. Allocation of weights**

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350 The fundamental premise adopted to build RESSICOM is the equal balance among the
351 four sustainability dimensions (Diaz-Sarachaga et al., 2016), which is crucial to enhance
352 sustainable development in urban areas. The distribution of indicators related to the sus-
353 tainability dimensions across the four domains involved in the new tool was uneven as
354 represented in Table 6, which includes 30, 6, 13 and 12 social, economic, environmental
355 and governance metrics, respectively.

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Table 6. Distribution of indicators across the dimensions (D) of sustainability

RES.#/D_{RES}	SUS.#/D_{SUS}	SAF.#/D_{SAF}	INC.#/D_{INC}
RES.1/ECO	SUS.1/SOC	SAF.1/SOC	INC.1/SOC
RES.2/SOC	SUS.2/ECO	SAF.2/SOC	INC.2/SOC
RES.3/GOV	SUS.3/ENV	SAF.3/SOC	INC.3/GOV
RES.4/SOC	SUS.4/ENV	SAF.4/SOC	INC.4/GOV
RES.5/GOV	SUS.5/ENV	SAF.5/SOC	INC.5/SOC
RES.6/GOV	SUS.6/GOV	SAF.6/ECO	INC.6/ECO
RES.7/SOC	SUS.7/SOC	SAF.7/GOV	INC.7/SOC
RES.8/SOC	SUS.8/SOC	SAF.8/SOC	INC.8/SOC
	SUS.9/ENV	SAF.9/SOC	INC.9/GOV
	SUS.10/ENV	SAF.10/SOC	INC.10/SOC
	SUS.11/ENV	SAF.11/SOC	INC.11/SOC
	SUS.12/ENV	SAF.12/GOV	INC.12/SOC
	SUS.13/ENV	SAF.13/SOC	INC.13/SOC
	SUS.14/ENV	SAF.14/SOC	INC.14/SOC
	SUS.15/ENV	SAF.15/ENV	INC.15/GOV
	SUS.16/ENV		INC.16/SOC
	SUS.17/ECO		INC.17/SOC
	SUS.18/GOV		
	SUS.19/ECO		
	SUS.20/GOV		
	SUS.21/ENV		

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The total scoring of RESSICOM shown in Table 5 involves a maximum of 140 points to be gained according to the fulfilment of the goals measured by the indicators. 25% of the total marks (35 points) was allocated to each dimension of sustainability to ensure the balance among them. Thus, the highest scores of the social, economic, environmental and governance dimensions encompassed 69, 15, 34 and 22 points, respectively. The weight w_j associated with a sustainability domain was determined based on the balanced aggregate of the upper scores (U) of each indicator i included in the dimension j , as formulated in Eq. (1).

$$w_j = \frac{0.25 * \sum_{i=1}^n U_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n U_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

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As a result, the weights for the social, economic, environmental and governance indicators were 0.51, 2.33, 1.03 and 1.59, ensuring that each dimension reached 25% of the maximum score of RESSICOM. The multiplication of the thresholds for the mandatory indicators by the abovementioned weights enabled determining 4 levels of achievement according to the sum of all the weighted scores across the four domains covered by the new rating system. In the case of surpassing the minimum weighted score resulting for each domain (11.74, 29.49, 18.08 and 16.91, respectively), the evalu-

376 ated city would receive the designation of resilient, sustainable, safe or inclusive. Plati-
377 num City is the title assigned to cities holding all the denominations at once.
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379 **3. Results and discussion: a case study in Mexico City**

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381 Mexico City is one of the most populous places in the world and the second one in Latin
382 America, with 8.9 million residents representing a population density of 5,954.2 per-
383 sons/km², and more than 21 millions of inhabitants in the metropolitan area. More than
384 30% of economic activity of the country is produced in this area, having a Gross Do-
385 mestic Product per capita of 20,358.9 USD (INEGI, 2018). This megacity experiences
386 diverse challenges involving resilience, sustainability, inclusiveness and safety, as a
387 consequence of growing urbanization. Floods in the rainy season and frequent earth-
388 quakes are the most common hazards that hit the city. The earthquake occurred in Sep-
389 tember 1985, which reached a magnitude of 8.1 at the Richter scale, caused more than
390 25,000 fatalities, ruining 412 buildings and damaging 3,124 more, including 13 hospi-
391 tals (UNISDR, 2018). Last September 2017, a seism with a magnitude of 7.1 devastated
392 the city, leaving hundreds of deaths and thousands of damaged buildings (UNISDR,
393 2018).

394 Despite the stunning negative effects of urbanization and the increased frequency of
395 hazard events in Mexico City, only a few attempts have been reported to evaluate this
396 city in terms of sustainability and resilience. Delgado-Ramos and Guibrinet (2017)
397 proposed a set of Urban Sustainability and Resilience Indicators to be applied to Mexico
398 City, whilst the Rockefeller Foundation launched the Mexico City Resilience Strategy
399 in September 2016 (Rockefeller, 2016) as part of the global initiative 100 Resilient Cit-
400 ies. The catastrophic earthquake of 2017 served to ascertain that the development and
401 implementation of this resilience strategy required a profound revision. In order to con-
402 tribute to enhance the living conditions of citizens in Mexico City from a holistic ap-
403 proach, this megacity was selected as a suitable case study for the application of
404 RESSICOM. The information necessary to implement the system was collected from
405 several sources from the government of Mexico City, such as the Statistical and Geo-
406 graphical Yearbook (INEGI, 2016a), the National Health and Nutrition Survey
407 (ENSANUT, 2016), the National Household Income and Expenditure Survey (INEGI,
408 2016b), the Intercensal Survey (INEGI, 2015), the World Bank (World Bank, 2018) and
409 the OECD (OECD, 2017).

410 4.67 marks were awarded to RES.1 because the SAIDI index was 34.74. The exces-
411 sive length of water supply disruption (RES.2) and the lack of analysis about redundan-
412 cy of critical services (RES.4) were penalized with 0 marks. The outdated map of risks
413 of the city gave 1.59 points to RES.3. However, the implementation of additional early
414 warning systems and an emergency plan covering regular drills rewarded RES.5 and
415 RES.6 with 3.18 points each. Since the annual interruption of at least 80% of health and

416 educational services took 2 and 8 days respectively, RES.7 and RES.8 scored 1.01 and
417 0.51 marks, respectively.

418 The proportion of family income that residents spent on housing (SUS.1) was below
419 15%, being rewarded with 1.01 marks. By contrast, SUS.2, SUS.4, SUS.5, SUS.7,
420 SUS.10, SUS.13, SUS.14, SUS.15, SUS.18, SUS.20, SUS.21 received 0 points, since
421 their values were below the minimum thresholds. SUS.3, SUS.9 and SUS.11 were all
422 graded with 2.06 marks. Whilst the first indicator proved that more than 20% of energy
423 stemmed from renewable source, the two others amounted to 724 annual fares and 28
424 m² of public green areas per capita, respectively. The reward for SUS.12 was 1.03
425 points, because urban land consumption per resident was 65.77 m². The open-source
426 description of municipal departments' liabilities gave 1.59 marks to SUS.6. About 5%
427 of urban dwellers commuted by walking and/or bicycle (SUS.8), receiving 0.51 points.
428 A score of 3.09 was earned by SUS.16 due to the low annual emission of carbon per
429 capita, which rounded 3.41 ton. SUS.17 and SUS.19 scored 2.33 points each. The for-
430 mer reflected 2.42% of externally funded local budget, whilst the latter was above 10%
431 of manufacturing employment rate.

432 SAF.1, SAF.2, SAF.6, SAF.8, SAF.9, SAF.10 and SAF.12 were below their mini-
433 mum thresholds and, therefore, scored 0 points. Between 90 and 100% of population
434 had regular access to drinkable water, power and sanitation facilities, which is why
435 SAF.3, SAF.4 and SAF.5 were rewarded with 0.51 marks. Since a proportion between
436 60 and 75% of urban inhabitants felt safe in the city and were covered by public health
437 services, SAF.11 and SAF.13 gained 0.51 points each. SAF.14 also scored 0.51 marks,
438 due to the rate of 2.86 beds in public hospitals per 1,000 inhabitants. Because all urban
439 population was covered by solid waste collection, SAF.15 was rewarded with 1.03
440 points. Transparent systems to fight against corruption were implemented, such that
441 SAF.7 received 1.59 marks.

442 INC.4, INC.6, INC.7, INC.8, INC.9, INC.11, INC.12, INC.15 and INC.16 showed
443 very low values receiving 0 points each. On the contrary, INC.3 was graded with 1.59
444 points, since there was a public map including all municipal stakeholders related to sus-
445 tainability and resilience matters. 11% of slum dwellers, 83 minutes of average com-
446 muting time and 67.90 % of population with internet connection were the values of
447 INC.1, INC.13 and INC.14, which resulted in 0.51 points each. Since the GINI coeffi-
448 cient was 0.45, INC.10 received 0.28 points. Lastly, INC.2, INC.5 and INC.17 graded
449 1.01 marks each, due to the values of 0.25% homeless rate and 67.24% participation in
450 the last municipal election, as well as the existence of a census for indigenous people.

451 After applying RESSICOM according to the values summarized in Table 7, Mexico
452 City scored 14.14, 18.07, 5.68 and 6.43 points in the resilience, sustainability, safety
453 and inclusiveness domains, respectively. Since their thresholds are 11.74, 29.49, 18.08
454 and 16.91, Mexico City can only be defined as a Resilient City.

Table 7. Assessment of Mexico City using RESSICOM

RES.#	Value	Unweighted /Weighted Score	SUS.#	Value	Unweighted /Weighted Score	SAF.#	Value	Unweighted /Weighted Score	INC.#	Indicator Value	Unweighted /Weighted Score
RES.1	34.74	2.00/4.67	SUS.1	9.50%	2.00/1.01	SAF.1	26.70%	0.00/0.00	INC.1	11.00%	1.00/0.51
RES.2	82	0.00/0.00	SUS.2	11.77%	0.00/0.00	SAF.2	12.30%	0.00/0.00	INC.2	0.25%	2.00/1.01
RES.3	yes	1.00/1.59	SUS.3	22.40%	2.00/2.06	SAF.3	99.63%	1.00/0.51	INC.3	yes	1.00/1.59
RES.4	no	0.00/0.00	SUS.4	0.00%	0.00/0.00	SAF.4	97.67%	1.00/0.51	INC.4	no	0.00/0.00
RES.5	yes	2.00/3.18	SUS.5	40.00%	0.00/0.00	SAF.5	99.07%	1.00/0.51	INC.5	67.24%	2.00/1.01
RES.6	yes	2.00/3.18	SUS.6	yes	1.00/1.59	SAF.6	43.40%	0.00/0.00	INC.6	31.67%	0.00/0.00
RES.7	2	2.00/1.01	SUS.7	72.50%	0.00/0.00	SAF.7	yes	1.00/1.59	INC.7	27.20%	0.00/0.00
RES.8	8	1.00/0.51	SUS.8	5.00%	1.00/0.51	SAF.8	33.00%	0.00/0.00	INC.8	16.50%	0.00/0.00
			SUS.9	724	2.00/2.06	SAF.9	950.05	0.00/0.00	INC.9	no	0.00/0.00
			SUS.10	58	0.00/0.00	SAF.10	16.26	0.00/0.00	INC.10	0.45	0.55/0.28
			SUS.11	28	2.00/2.06	SAF.11	64.62%	1.00/0.51	INC.11	24.19%	0.00/0.00
			SUS.12	65.77	1.00/1.03	SAF.12	23.00	0.00/0.00	INC.12	54.05%	0.00/0.00
			SUS.13	51	0.00/0.00	SAF.13	67.44%	1.00/0.51	INC.13	83	1.00/0.51
			SUS.14	60	0.00/0.00	SAF.14	2.86	1.00/0.51	INC.14	67.90%	1.00/0.51
			SUS.15	130	0.00/0.00	SAF.15	100.00%	1.00/1.03	INC.15	no	0.00/0.00
			SUS.16	3.41	3.00/3.09				INC.16	11.40%	0.00/0.00
			SUS.17	2.42%	1.00/2.33				INC.17	yes	2.00/1.01
			SUS.18	7.69%	0.00/0.00						
			SUS.19	10.76%	1.00/2.33						
			SUS.20	47.33%	0.00/0.00						
			SUS.21	10.00%	0.00/0.00						
Total Resilience		10.00/14.14	Total Sustainability		16.00/18.07	Total Safety		8.00/5.68	Total Inclusiveness		10.55/6.43

457 In terms of resilience, the performance of the city was satisfactory. Unlike RES.2,
458 RES.3 and RES.4, other indicators (RES.1, RES.5, RES.6, RES.7 and RES.8) reached
459 or exceeded the minimum score required. Service disruption lengths were acceptable
460 except for water supply. Furthermore, the city failed in both analyzing the redundancy
461 of basic services and updating its urban risk map. However, the existence of an emer-
462 gency plan and early warning systems, coupled with the conduct of drills, provided rel-
463 evant support in case of disaster.

464 Regarding the assessment of sustainability, the results were poor. Less than half of
465 the indicators surpassed the thresholds established by the system, i.e. SUS.1, SUS.3,
466 SUS.6, SUS.8, SUS.9, SUS.11, SUS.12, SUS.16, SUS.17 and SUS.19. Instead, other
467 metrics failed to meet the minimum requirements of RESSICOM. The reduction on
468 water and power use was negligible, whilst losses from water network were extremely
469 high (about 40%), exacerbating the lack of water supply in some districts. The high
470 emissions of pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and SO₂) jeopardized citizens' health; however,
471 carbon emissions per capita were low due to the high population of the city. The rate of
472 overweight people was very high. Urban residents were not satisfied with public re-
473 sources, experiencing a low expenditure on basic services. Traffic congestion was ex-
474 cessive, favoring the use of public transport and alternative commuting ways.

475 Only 3 out of 15 safety indicators passed the evaluation, which explained the low
476 score achieved by this domain. The rates of people living under the poverty line and
477 malnourished children were unacceptably high, as well as the proportion of population
478 with regular access to water and sanitation facilities. The metrics associated with crime
479 and corruption provided impressive values, confirming the critical situation of the city
480 in this sense, whereby more than 64% of its residents felt unsafe. Time emergency re-
481 sponse was too high (23 min), whilst almost one-third of the population was not covered
482 by public health services.

483 Despite 8 inclusiveness-related metrics reached their corresponding mandatory
484 points, the total score of the domain was very poor. The involvement of residents in
485 decision-making processes was almost null, as well as the integration of migrants
486 through local policies. Informal employment and youth unemployment exceeded 25%.
487 The enrollment in secondary education experienced a significant decline in comparison
488 with students in primary school for both genders and only females. Moreover, the gen-
489 der wage gap was 16.5%. Those findings underpinned a GINI coefficient of 0.45, re-
490 flecting that Mexico City suffers from inequality.

491 The findings of this research are similar to those highlighted in the assessment con-
492 ducted by Delgado-Ramos and Guibrunet (2017), who underlined decarbonisation, air
493 pollution, informal settlements, inadequate and obsolete water infrastructure, corrup-
494 tion, urban land expansion and unsustainable mobility as key issues in Mexico City. In
495 the same vein, RESSICOM identified pollution, basic services, crime, corruption, un-
496 employment and education as major concerns in the city. Water, sanitation and health

497 services were not accessible for all the population, whilst the plans to reduce water and
498 power consumption were ineffective. Water leakage was extremely large and the health
499 of residents was undermined by high levels of air emissions. Furthermore, crime and
500 corruption, unemployment rates (at all ages) and low secondary schooling levels hin-
501 dered the local economic growth. The implementation of effective mid/long term plans
502 to reduce the effects of growing urbanization in terms of critical services could contrib-
503 ute to enhancing wellbeing. Moreover, new inclusive policies might help integrating
504 migrants and reducing social and gender inequalities.

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506 **4. Conclusions**

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508 In order to cover the deficit found in existing rating systems, which are mainly oriented
509 towards the evaluation of either resilience or sustainability, this article developed a new
510 framework to jointly assess the Resilience, Sustainability, Safety and Inclusiveness of
511 Communities and Cities (RESSICOM). It compiled major concerns gathered by several
512 global initiatives such as the 2030 Agenda, the New Urban Agenda and the Sendai
513 Framework and used Mexico City as a case study for its application. The main conclu-
514 sions drawn from this research are summarized as follows:

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- Urbanization boosts the close interconnection among the four domains contem-
plated in the system, affecting all sustainability dimensions: social, economic,
environmental and governance aspects. For instance, the massive arrival of mi-
grants to cities for a better live creates pockets of poverty that accentuate ine-
qualities. Emerging marginalized groups occupy vulnerable locations to natural
disasters, whose occurrence produces more poverty and increases socio-
economic gaps to close the circle.
- The social dimension and the sustainability domain reflected the highest amount
of indicators in the new system, with 30 and 21 items each. Conversely, econo-
my and resilience only gathered 6 and 8 metrics, respectively.
- The indirect effects of each domain on the others are not appraised by
RESSICOM, such as the impact of high crime rates on economic growth or the
influence of long commutes on employees' performance or people health. The
measure of these correlations requires citizens' involvement through question-
naires, workshops and fieldwork.
- RESSICOM emphasized the relevance of the governance dimension to provide
effective frameworks and policies related to, inter alia, risk management, emer-
gency plans, population involvement, corruption fight, migrants and minority
groups' integration and public attention.
- Regarding the case study, Mexico City revealed significant gaps in sustainabil-
ity, safety and inclusiveness matters. Although the resilience threshold was
reached, the city still must face major challenges in this domain. Crime, corrup-

537 tion, pollution, unemployment, secondary education enrolment and the efficient
538 management of basic services were identified as main issues to be addressed.

539 RESSICOM can be deemed as a great point of departure to delve into the construc-
540 tion of new tools to assess cities through a holistic approach focused on enhancing the
541 living conditions of dwellers. However, it lacks the contribution of inhabitants who can
542 provide new views to incorporate additional indicators to the system in forthcoming
543 revisions. Furthermore, the weights of the indicators in RESSICOM could also be re-
544 considered after evaluating citizens' concerns.

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- A new rating tool (RESSICOM) was designed to assess urban development holistically
- RESSICOM jointly considered resilience, sustainability, safety and inclusiveness
- The indicators of RESSICOM were weighted to balance the pillars of sustainability
- The proposed framework was tested using Mexico City as a representative case study
- The results showed that Mexico City was not sustainable, safe and inclusive enough

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